

A comparison of simplified modeling approaches and simulation quality of an industrial R717-HTHP

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ABSTRACT

The industrial sector offers considerable potential for reducing energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions through the use of high-temperature heat pumps (HTHPs). In this context, simulations can serve as a useful tool to pinpoint optimization opportunities for the process heat supply and its interaction with subsystems. However, as the complexity of the calculations and the effort required for model parameterization escalate with the level of detail, certain simplifications are necessary.

This study describes the development of simplified simulation models of an ammonia (R717) chiller (nominal cooling capacity: 900 kW, source outlet temperature of 1 °C) and an add-on HTHP (nominal heating capacity: 550 kW, sink outlet temperatures up to 90 °C). For this purpose, different model approaches, such as second law efficiencies and component-based modeling using UA-values, are explored and evaluated through a comparative analysis of simulation quality. Validation is conducted using measurement data at varying operating conditions, which shows mean errors in sink & source capacities and COPs below 5.2 %.

Keywords: Ammonia, Waste Heat Recovery, Dairy, CIP, Modelica

1 INTRODUCTION

Many industrial processes, particularly in the food industry, are characterized by a simultaneous cooling and heating demand. Furthermore, if the cooling demand is already covered by a chiller, a high-temperature heat pump (HTHP) can utilize the waste heat of the chiller and lift it to temperature levels necessary for the supplied process. Since HTHPs can be an alternative to fossil-fueled process heat supply, they can significantly contribute to a decarbonization and efficiency increase in the food industry – in particular in the dairy sector due to the continuously occurring cooling demand. To give a figure of magnitude, in 2017 the dairies in the EU processed 158.6 Mt of milk to 119 Mt of products (Eurostat, 2018). Keller et al. (2016) report a demand of steam between 0.4 MJ·kg⁻¹ for ultra-high-temperature processed milk and 2.4 MJ·kg⁻¹ for concentrated milk. This study focuses on a HTHP which upgrades the waste heat from a chiller installed at an Austrian dairy plant.

The HTHP supplies a cleaning-in-place (CIP) facility for milk transport trucks. To analyze system behavior, considering interactions among the chiller, HTHP, and CIP system under varying operating conditions, simulation models are employed. Given the substantial impact of simulation model complexity on modeling, parameterization, and computational requirements, two simulation models of varying detail are presented and compared with plant measurement data to assess accuracy.

The first approach covers a (simplified) “physical” component-based modeling. This allows for a comprehensive investigation of the chiller and HTHP, including circuit design, control parameters in the refrigerant (and external) circuits, etc. while considering the impact on fluid properties, performance, etc. The component-based simulation model therefore incorporates compressor efficiencies, UA-values, etc. The second approach employs a “Lorenz-cycle”-efficiency model which results in a loss of information – e.g., no direct consideration of the refrigerant circuit. However, capacities and COPs can be calculated with remarkable efficiency, which is crucial for simulation-based investigations of industrial processes. These characteristics can then be utilized for the investigation of the chiller’s & HTHP’s interaction with other system components.

2 HEAT PUMP

In an Austrian dairy, a R717 chiller with a nominal evaporator capacity of 900 kW was solely used to produce chilled water at a temperature of 1 °C (“ $t_{CH,SO,out}$ ”) to meet the cooling demands. The heat rejected in the condenser was dissipated using a cooling tower. To reduce the energy demand of the dairy’s cleaning-in-place (CIP) system, which operates at temperatures up to 90 °C, the R717 chiller was extended with a directly integrated add-on “high” temperature heat pump (HTHP), which uses part of the chiller’s rejected heat. In the following, the refrigerant cycle (chiller and HTHP) is explained with reference to Figure 1.

Figure 1: left: Simplified scheme of the chiller & HTHP and cleaning-in-place-system; right: t/h-diagram of the chiller & HTHP

2.1. Chiller

In the chiller, the low-pressure separator (“LP-Sep”) receives partly evaporated refrigerant (ammonia – R717) from the evaporator and a two-phase flow from the chiller’s expansion valve (“EXV_{CH}”) which is used to control the “LP-Sep’s” liquid level. The density of the liquid refrigerant in the “LP-Sep” causes a natural circulation through the evaporator (“EVAP” in Figure 1), where it absorbs heat from the heat source, i.e. cold water (“ $t_{CH,SO,in}$ ”). The vaporous refrigerant from “LP-Sep” is compressed from low-pressure to mean-pressure by a reciprocating compressor (“LP-COMP”). The speed of the compressor is controlled using the cold-water outlet temperature as control variable. The mean pressure in “MP-Sep” is controlled using “Valve_{CH,4}” which divides the refrigerant flow between the “cooling tower” and the HTHP cycle.

After rejecting heat to the ambient in the cooling tower, (subcooled) refrigerant is accumulated in the mean-pressure receiver (“MP-Rec”), which also receives refrigerant from the HTHP’s mean-pressure separator (“MP-Sep”) – the pressure in “MP-Rec” is determined by their mixing ratio.

2.2. Add-on “high” temperature heat pump (HTHP)

When the HTHP is in operation, the check valve “Valve_{HP,10}” is open, part of the gaseous R717 from the “LP-COMP” (i.e., the flow which is not directed to the “cooling tower” via “Valve_{CH,4}”) streams to the mean-pressure separator (“MP-Sep”), whose filling level is controlled by “Valve_{HP,13}”.

The MP-Sep receives two-phase refrigerant leaving the HTHP's expansion valve ("EXV_{HP}") too. Vaporous refrigerant from the "MP-Sep" is compressed by a reciprocating compressor ("HP-COMP") from mean-pressure to high-pressure and operates at a controlled speed. After the "HP-Comp", the refrigerant is desuperheated (in "DESUP") and condensed (in "CON") by rejecting heat to a water circuit which heats up to 90 °C (" $t_{HP,SI,out}$ ") and is circulated between the CIP and the HTHP. Due to the size of these heat exchangers, the refrigerant might leave – operating-point depended – "DESUP" in superheated or two-phase state and the "CON" in two-phase, saturated or subcooled state. After leaving "CON", the refrigerant flows to the high-pressure receiver ("HP-Rec"). Further on, the refrigerant is subcooled in the subcooler ("SUB") by rejecting heat to the water circuit in parallel to "CON". The subcooling of the refrigerant is controlled by "Valve_{HP,SUBC}" in the water circuit. After subcooling, the refrigerant is throttled in "EXV_{HP}" to mean-pressure and streams into "MP-Sep". Refrigerant streams from through "Valve_{HP,13}" to "MP-Rec" and enters the "chiller-cycle".

3 SIMULATION MODELS

In this chapter, two simulation models representing different levels of detail are presented. The first simulation model uses a (simplified) "physical" component-wise modeling, while the second simulation model uses second law efficiencies. Both simulation models are validated and compared using measurement data representing various operating conditions of the R717-chiller and HTHP.

3.1. Component-based simulation model

The R717-HP was modeled in DYMOLA (DYMOLA, 2021) using Modelica Code (Modelica, 2020) and corresponds to the structure and the control circuits shown in Figure 1 and described in chapter 2.

While the components of the refrigerant cycle were modelled by the authors, the Modelica Standard Library v3.2.3+build.4 (MSL v3.2.3) (Modelica, 2020) is used for the external water circuits connected to the heat pump (see Figure 1).

For the calculation of the property data of the fluids, the following correlations and libraries are used:

- Water properties: IAPWS (2008), provided by: MSL v3.2.3 (Modelica, 2020)
- Moist air properties: Verein Deutscher Ingenieure (2013), provided by: MSL v3.2.3 (Modelica, 2020)
- R717 properties: Gao et al. (2020), provided by Coolprop v6.0 (Bell et al., 2014)

In the development of the simulation model, an emphasis was placed on simplified modeling approaches that allow for the computation of the model in a relatively short period of time while maintaining sufficient accuracy. Therefore, different approaches for the modeling of components were analyzed and evaluated in terms of computation time and simulation quality. The final modeling approaches are shown below:

- The compressor model uses volumetric and isentropic efficiencies (heat pump specific correlations were taken from Verdnik et al., 2022) to determine mass flows and compressor powers.
- The valve model assumes isenthalpic expansion yielding sufficiently accurate results despite not being physically exact.
- The receiver model uses lumped vessel correlations assuming saturated liquid or vapor at the outlets when a liquid level is given. The receiver model calculates changes in saturation pressure and includes hydrostatic pressure.

For the modeling of these components, it is referred to Rieberer et al. (2022).

Calculation of heat transfer that includes phase change has a significant impact on accuracy but also offers great potential for reducing computation time. Therefore, a simplified approach for a moving boundary heat exchanger (MBHE)-model using UA-values was developed and is presented in the following section.

3.2. Simplified MBHE-model

There are a large number of modeling approaches for simulating heat transfer – from very detailed models to calculate heat transfer in an almost arbitrary number of cells using heat transfer coefficients (HTC) and pressure drop correlations (as provided by TIL (TLK-Thermo, 2021)) to very simplified approaches using only efficiency characteristics and constant pressure drops (as provided by AixLib, 2021).

Both approaches differ in the accuracy of the results as well as in computation time. A modeling approach, that is suitable for enabling short calculation times and offers an acceptable accuracy, is the moving boundary approach (Desideri et al., 2016). In MBHE, the heat transfer rate is calculated in up to three zones, each containing a state of the refrigerant (see Figure 2). For the calculation, the application of HTC-correlations is widely used and presented in many works (e.g., McKinley and Alleyne, 2008 as well as Gräber et al., 2010).

Figure 2: State-dependent “zones” in a condenser (“ \dot{Q}_{Con} (e.g.)”): an example of transferred heat capacity)

Contrary to the previously described models, the present approach employs operating point-dependent total UA-values (the correlations developed from measured data are shown in APPENDIX A), while assuming equal U-values in all (3) zones. Consequently, the use of UA-values is limited to predicting steady-state operation resulting in a loss of accuracy. However, this approach offers a great opportunity for simplification (and gains in computational time as, e.g., no calculation of transport properties or Nusselt-correlations is needed to determine heat transfer). To account for phase change in the heat exchanger, the heat flows in each zone are calculated iteratively by adjusting the zone’s UA-value in regards to the total UA-value.

To avoid time-consuming calculation of fluid mass changes (during dynamic operation), within each zone a mean state is calculated and used for the calculation of heat transfer and fluid properties. This leads to a loss of accuracy, but is sufficient enough, when, e.g., heat flows, mass flows as well as pressures and thermal inertia, etc. are needed for the analysis of the heat pump’s behavior and its control (e.g., within a simulation comprising heat pump and the cleaning in place system). To enable a use for the investigation of transient behavior, a delay element (which also increases numerical stability) is used at the heat exchanger outlets.

The modeling approach is described below and illustrated on the basis of a condenser, in which desuperheating and partly condensation occur (see “ \dot{Q}_{Con} (e.g.)” in Figure 2).

To calculate heat flows using UA-values, the correlations in Eq. (1) and Eq. (2) are applied.

$$\dot{Q}_{\Delta T, \log, m} = UA \cdot \Delta T_{\log, m} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

with an arithmetic log mean temperature difference (e.g., for zone “A” in Figure 2) where ΔT_1 and ΔT_2 are the temperature differences between refrigerant and heat sink as shown in Figure 2.

$$\Delta T_{\log, m, A} = \frac{\Delta T_1 - \Delta T_2}{\ln(\Delta T_1 \cdot \Delta T_2^{-1})} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

According to Mattson (1997), this formula is badly conditioned if $\Delta T_1 \approx \Delta T_2$ and might result in divisions by zero. To avoid possibly occurring numerical errors, the calculation of $\Delta T_{\log, m}$ is based on Eq. (3) when $|\Delta T_1 - \Delta T_2| < 0.05 \cdot \max(\Delta T_1, \Delta T_2)$.

$$\Delta T_{\log,m,\text{approx}}=0.5 \cdot (\Delta T_1+\Delta T_2) \cdot \left[1-\frac{1}{12} \cdot \frac{(\Delta T_1-\Delta T_2)^2}{\Delta T_1 \cdot \Delta T_2} \cdot \left(1-\frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{(\Delta T_1-\Delta T_2)^2}{\Delta T_1 \cdot \Delta T_2} \right) \right] \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

By calculating $\Delta T_{\log,m}$ via Eq. (3) and not via Eq. (2) causes a relative error less than 10^{-5} according to Mattson (1997) – e.g. $\Delta T_1=6.66$ K, $\Delta T_2=7$ K $\rightarrow \Delta T_{\log,m}=6.8286$ K; $\Delta T_{\log,m,5\text{pprox.}}=6.8286$ K; relative error of $\delta_{T,\log,m,5\text{pprox.}}: <1.65 \cdot 10^{-7}$.

To calculate the phase boundaries of the single phases (e.g., superheated in zone “A” in Figure 2) of the refrigerant, the energy balance shown in Eq. (4) is used, where \dot{m}_{Ref} stands for the refrigerant mass flow, h_{in} for the specific enthalpy of the refrigerant at the inlet and h_a for the specific enthalpy at the outlet of the superheated zone. $\dot{Q}_{A,\Delta T,\log,m}$ is calculated according to Eq. (1) using Eq. (2) or Eq. (3).

$$0=\dot{m}_{\text{Ref}} \cdot (h_a-h_{\text{in}})+\dot{Q}_{A,\Delta T,\log,m} \quad \text{Eq. (4)}$$

In the following, by comparing h_a and the specific enthalpy at the dew point of the refrigerant ($h_{\text{sat},v}$) it is checked if the UA-value used does not result in an overlap of phase boundaries and therefore is correct for the calculation of the superheated zone’s capacity:

- If $h_a \geq h_{\text{sat},v}$, no phase transition occurs, and the heat exchanger segment contains one zone only resulting in calculation of heat transfer rate according to Eq. (1).
- If $h_a < h_{\text{sat},v}$, a phase transition occurs (i.e. $c_p \neq \text{const.}$) which has to be considered.

In case “a)” the heat transfer calculation is complete, meaning that the heat exchanger is capable to desuperheat only. In case “b)” the heat exchanger’s heat transfer characteristic (the overall UA-value) enables it to (partly) condense the refrigerant too.

In case “b)”, the calculation of the heat flow in the superheated zone is adjusted based on Eq. (5) considering the refrigerant’s enthalpy difference between dew point and the heat exchanger inlet. Additionally, the two-phase zone is “activated” and Eq. (6) is used to calculate the share (“ y_A ”) of zone A’s UA-value in the overall UA-value.

$$\dot{Q}_A=\dot{m}_{\text{Ref}} \cdot (h_{\text{in}}-h_{\text{sat},v}) \quad \text{Eq. (5)}$$

$$y_A=\frac{UA_A}{UA}=\frac{\dot{m}_{\text{Ref}} \cdot (h_{\text{in}}-h_{\text{sat},v})}{UA \cdot \Delta T_{\log,m,A}} \quad \text{Eq. (6)}$$

For the zone containing two-phase fluid (zone “B” in Figure 2), the energy balance is calculated using Eq. (7) under consideration of ΔT_2 and ΔT_3 for the calculation of $\Delta T_{\log,m,B}$ (see Eq. (2) and Eq. (3)). The specific enthalpy at the outlet of the condensing zone (h_b) is calculated using Eq. (8).

$$\dot{Q}_{B,\Delta T,\log,m}=UA \cdot (1-y_A) \cdot \Delta T_{\log,m,B} \quad \text{Eq. (7)}$$

$$0=\dot{m}_{\text{Ref}} \cdot (h_b-h_a)+\dot{Q}_{B,\Delta T,\log,m} \quad \text{Eq. (8)}$$

The term $(1-y_A)$ accounts for the calculation of UA_B (see Eq. (9)).

$$UA_B=UA-UA \cdot y_A=UA-UA_A \quad \text{Eq. (9)}$$

In the following, by comparing h_b and the specific enthalpy at the bubble point of the refrigerant ($h_{sat,l}$) it is checked if the UA-value used does not result in an overlap of phase boundaries and therefore is correct for the calculation of the two-phase zone's capacity:

- a) If $h_b \geq h_{sat,l}$, no phase transition occurs, and the heat exchanger segment contains one zone only resulting in calculation of heat transfer rate according to Eq. (7).
- b) If $h_b < h_{sat,l}$, a phase transition occurs (i.e. $c_p \neq \text{const.}$) which has to be considered.

In case "a" the heat transfer calculation is complete, meaning that the heat exchanger is capable to desuperheat and condensate (partly) only (which is the case for the example shown in Figure 2).

In case "b" the heat exchanger's heat transfer characteristic (the total UA-value) enables it to subcool the refrigerant too. Therefore, the calculation of the heat flow in the two-phase zone is adjusted based on Eq. (10) and the subcooled zone is "activated".

$$\dot{Q}_B = \dot{m}_{\text{Ref}} \cdot (h_{\text{sat},v} - h_{\text{sat},l}) \quad \text{Eq. (10)}$$

The outlet enthalpy at the subcooled zone is calculated using Eq. (11) under consideration of ΔT_3 and ΔT_4 for the calculation of $\Delta T_{\log,m,C}$.

$$0 = \dot{m}_{\text{Ref}} \cdot (h_c - h_b) + UA \cdot (1 - \gamma_A - \gamma_B) \cdot \Delta T_{\log,m,C} \quad \text{Eq. (11)}$$

The share (" γ_B ") of zone B's UA-value in the overall UA-value is calculated using Eq. (12).

$$\gamma_B = \frac{UA_B}{UA} = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{Ref}} \cdot (h_{\text{sat},v} - h_{\text{sat},l})}{UA \cdot \Delta T_{\log,m,B}} \quad \text{Eq. (12)}$$

3.3. Second law efficiency model

A very simplified calculation of refrigeration cycles' performance, particularly for simulation purposes, can be achieved by applying performance factors on ideal reference cycles ("second law models"). Within this work, this is shown by using simulation results of Eliskases (2023) who calculated COPs using "Lorenz-cycle"-efficiencies (see Eq. (13)) averaged from measurement data ($v_{\text{CH,C}} = 0.5128$, $v_{\text{HP,H}} = 0.4588$).

The utilization of the "Lorenz-cycle" facilitates the incorporation of polytropic state transitions, assuming that the refrigerant undergoes temperature changes analogous to those of the heat sources and sinks. This approach allows for the utilization of external temperatures, such as those of the heat source, to determine the ideal COP for both the chiller and heat pump, as outlined by Eliskases (2023) in the accompanying equations (see Eq. (13) - Eq. (15)). Within his work, the interconnection of the chiller and heat pump was established using the saturation temperature (T_{sat}) at mean pressure (p_m), where the pressure values for the chiller ($p_{\text{CH},2}$) and heat pump ($p_{\text{HP},1}$) are approximately equivalent ($p_m \approx p_{\text{CH},2} \approx p_{\text{HP},1}$).

$$v = \frac{COP_{\text{CH/HP}}}{COP_{\text{Lorenz,CH/HP}}} \quad \text{Eq. (13)}$$

$$COP_{\text{Lorenz,CH}} = \frac{T_{\log,m,SO}}{T_{\text{sat}}(p_m) - T_{\log,m,SO}} \quad \text{Eq. (14)}$$

$$COP_{\text{Lorenz,HP}} = \frac{T_{\log,m,SI}}{T_{\log,m,SI} - T_{\text{sat}}(p_m)} \quad \text{Eq. (15)}$$

The logarithmic mean temperatures of the source ($T_{\log,m,SO}$) and sink ($T_{\log,m,SI}$) are calculated according to Eq. (16) and Eq. (17). Here, $T_{SO,in}$ & $T_{SO,out}$ describe the source inlet & outlet temperatures and $T_{SI,in}$ & $T_{SI,out}$ the sink inlet & outlet temperatures.

$$T_{\log,m,SO} = \frac{T_{SO,in} - T_{SO,out}}{\ln(T_{SO,in} \cdot T_{SO,out}^{-1})} \quad \text{Eq. (16)}$$

$$T_{\log,m,SI} = \frac{T_{SI,out} - T_{SI,in}}{\ln(T_{SI,out} \cdot T_{SI,in}^{-1})} \quad \text{Eq. (17)}$$

4 VALIDATION AND COMPARISON OF THE HEAT PUMP MODELS

To validate the simulation models, they are compared to measurement data from 30 reference operating points (OP) representing various operating conditions of the heat pump. The boundary conditions, derived from measurement data and utilized in the simulation, are shown in APPENDIX B .

The saturation temperature at mean pressure (in “MP-Sep”) is used as an input in the second law model (acc. to section 3.3). As with in the real R717-heat pump (see scheme in Figure 1), in the component model-based simulation (acc. to section 3.2), the pressure in “MP-Sep” is controlled using a valve (“Valve_{CH,4}” in Figure 1) and the pressure in “MP-Rec” results from the mixing ratio of the subcooled refrigerant entering from the cooling tower and the refrigerant entering from “MP-Sep”.

Figure 3 illustrates the comparison between measurement and simulation results, with crosses representing the use of component models (CM) and circles representing the use of the second law model (2nd law). To quantify deviations from measurement data, the relative error is calculated using Eq. (18), and the mean relative error is calculated using Eq. (19), where 'x' denotes the quantity (e.g., capacity, COP), 'meas' measurement data, 'a' the modeling approach and 'i' represents the operating point. Dashed lines denote a relative error of $\pm 5\%$, while solid lines represent a $\pm 10\%$ deviation of simulation results.

$$\delta_{x,a,i} = \frac{x_{sim,a,i} - x_{meas,i}}{x_{meas,i}} \quad \text{Eq. (18)}$$

$$\bar{\delta}_{x,a} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{j_{meas}} |\delta_{x,a,i}|}{j_{meas}} \quad \text{Eq. (19)}$$

4.1. Measurement uncertainties

According to Wagner et al. (2021), the small temperature difference on the external side between inlet and outlet ($\Delta T_{CH,SO} = t_{CH,SO,in} - t_{CH,SO,out} \approx 2-3$ K) at the evaporator of the chiller and the high volume flow rate ($\dot{V}_{CH,SO,in}$) result in a large calculated measurement uncertainty (e.g., of the evaporator capacity). Unfortunately, due to operational reasons, it was not possible to calibrate the temperature sensors before carrying out the measurements. Therefore, for measurement data evaluation, uncertainties of 0.5 K for temperature measurements and 1 % for volume flow rate measurements are assumed. This results in a calculated measurement uncertainty of ± 0.94 to ± 1.59 (± 21 % to ± 37 %) for the efficiency of the chiller (COP_C) at the selected operating points.

However, according to Wagner et al. (2021), the comparability of the different measuring points is given, as the systematic measurement uncertainty occurs equally at all measuring points and the source inlet/outlet temperature ($t_{CH,SO,in/out}$) was almost constant during the investigations. When investigating the performance of the HTHP, the measurement uncertainty of the temperature measurement at the external circuits has a much smaller effect on the efficiency of the HTHP (COP_H) with ± 0.09 to ± 0.51 (± 2.5 % to ± 13.3 %) and on the heating capacity ($\dot{Q}_{HP,SI}$) with ± 7 kW to ± 29 kW (± 2.5 % to ± 13.3 %) due to the larger temperature differences between inlet and outlet. When calculating the measurement uncertainties of COP_C and COP_H , the deviations caused by the frequency inverters were not considered as they are not clearly evident in the data sheets.

Since, as described, no precise information can be provided on the measurement uncertainties, the measurement uncertainties are not shown in the following figures and considered when discussing the simulation and measurement results.

4.2. Chiller

The comparison of the simulated and measured evaporator capacities (see Figure 3a) shows a close prediction of the chiller behavior. The largest deviation, -5.5 %, between the simulation and measurement occurs at OP 7. This suggests that the CM-simulation model may struggle to accurately reproduce high water volume flow scenarios combined with low compressor frequencies (Figure 3a).

The simulated compressor (Figure 3b) shows small deviations from the measured data, with the highest deviation in compressor power being 7 % when comparing the CM and measurement data at OP4, and a mean relative error of 2.6 %. The second-law model shows deviations of up to 5.3 % in OP7 and a mean deviation of 1.4 %. The reason for this is, that the compressor power of the second-law model is calculated from the COP using chiller capacities from measurement data.

Due to the deviations of the evaporator capacities and compressor power calculated by the CM, the second law model predicts the COP_c (Figure 3c) of the chiller compared to the CM model better. The second law model shows errors up to 5.7 % with a mean error of 1.4 % only. The CM model's largest error of 10 % in COP_c occurs at OP 23, where the compressor capacity is overestimated by 6.2 % and the evaporator capacity is underestimated by 4.3 %, resulting in mean relative error of 3.2 %.

Figure 3: Chiller: Stationary validation and comparison of two simulation models of different levels of detail (+: CM, o: 2nd law; dashed lines: relative error of $\pm 5\%$, solid lines: relative error of $\pm 10\%$)

4.3. Add-on “high” temperature heat pump (HTHP)

The simulated heat sink capacity (Figure 4a) shows a mean relative error of 3.5 %, with the highest error reaching 9.7 % at OP4. This peak is due to an overestimation of mass flows resulting in higher compressor, condenser and subcooler capacities while the desuperheater is underestimated. This suggests that the component models represent heat transfer at lower water volume flows less accurately, resulting in higher pressures and consequently higher compressor power.

The high compressor powers (Figure 4b) and pressures (Figure 4h) in the HTHP also affect the performance of the desuperheater, condenser, and subcooler. An overestimation of the high pressure by 1.5 bar in OP5 (Figure 4h) leads to the highest deviation of 8.6 % at OP5 in the simulated compressor (of the CM). However, in OP6, which shows similar operating conditions (see APPENDIX B), exhibits an error of only 1.2 %, indicating potential discrepancies in measured data. The second law model shows its highest deviation of compressor power (Figure 4b) at OP4 (deviation of 19.3 %, compared to the measurement data), where the mean pressure is increased by 2 bar compared to the other reference operating points. A comparison with the CM shows a deviation of about 20 %. The mean error of the compressor of the second law model is 4.1 %, while that of the component model is 2.3%.

The most significant deviations between the simulation model and the measurement data are observed in almost all OPs of the desuperheater (Figure 4e) and subcooler (Figure 4g). This can also be seen in the large mean relative errors, which, especially in the case of the subcooler. However, the errors show opposite trends, which is why they partially cancel each other out at most measurement points. In addition, the desuperheater and the subcooler account for a small part of the sink capacity only. These reasons lead to small errors of the heat sink capacities (Figure 4a) with good estimates of the condenser capacities (Figure 4f).

Therefore, the COP_H (Figure 4c) of the second law model exhibits larger deviations compared to the CM, which shows a mean error of 2.9 %. The highest deviation of the CM occurs when the compressor power is overestimated at OP4 resulting in a mean error of 4.1 %. However, the second law model calculated the COP_{OV} (Figure 4d) with higher accuracy compared to the CM. One of the reasons for this is that in the CM, both the source and sink capacity are calculated (resulting in errors compared to measurement data) while they are used as inputs in the second law model (and therefore show no errors).

Figure 4: HTHP: Stationary validation and comparison of two simulation models of different levels of detail (+: CM, o: 2nd law; dashed lines: relative error of $\pm 5\%$, solid lines: relative error of $\pm 10\%$)

Figure 4: HTHP: Stationary validation and comparison of two simulation models of different levels of detail (+: CM, o: 2nd law; dashed lines: relative error of $\pm 5\%$, solid lines: relative error of $\pm 10\%$)

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the modeling and simulations results of simplified component models and second law approaches for an industrial R717-heat pump. The component models are interconnected to replicate the circuit structure of the heat pump system and use heat pump-specific correlations for UA-values and compressor efficiencies to compute the chiller and heat pump behavior. On the other hand, a second law model is parameterized based on a second law efficiency. The comparison of simulation and measurement results indicate that both simulation models can effectively represent the heat pump's operating characteristics with mean deviations below 5.2 %. This suggests that both simulation models offer promising potential to mimic the behavior of the industrial heat pump, both with different applications: The second law model provides a rapid mean to analyze further integration of processes supplied by the heat pump and needs 15 ms only for the calculation of an operating point (in comparison, the CM-simulation model needs 70 s for the calculation of a stationary operating point – moreover, it also requires greater effort for modelling and parameterization, of components and control circuits). However, the second law model requires source or sink capacity or compressor powers as inputs while the component model-based simulation allows for the analysis of various component characteristics (such as UA-values, mass flows, etc.) and facilitates testing and analysis of heat pump control strategies.

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NOMENCLATURE

δ	relative error	\dot{m}	mass flow rate ($\text{kg} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$)
$\bar{\delta}$	mean relative error	meas	measured
Δ	difference	MP	mean pressure
ν	Lorenz-cycle efficiency	n	Compressor speed ($1 \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$)
τ	time (s)	out	outlet
a	modeling approach	OV	overall
A, B, C	heat exchanger “zones”	p	pressure (bar)
c_p	Specific heat capacity ($\text{kJ} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$)	P	power (kW)
C	cooling	q	vapour fraction ($\text{kg}_v \cdot \text{kg}_{v+i}^{-1}$)
CIP	cleaning-in-place	\dot{Q}	heat flow rate (kW)
CH	chiller	Rec	Receiver
COP	coefficient of performance (-)	sat	saturated
CON	condenser	Sep	separator
COMP	compressor	SI	sink
DESUP	desuperheater	sim	simulated
EXV	expansion valve	SO	source
h	specific enthalpy ($\text{kJ} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$)	sub	subcooled
H	heating	SUBC	subcooler
HP	Heat pump	t	temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
HTHP	High-temperature heat pump	T	temperature (K)
i, OP	Operating point	UA	heat transition coefficient ($\text{kW} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$)
in	inlet	v	vaporous
j	total number of measured OP	\dot{V}	volume flow rate ($\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$)
l	liquid	x	quantity
log	logarithmic	y	relative zone size (-)
m	mean		

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APPENDIX A – Correlations for the calculation of operating condition dependent UA-values (in kW · K⁻¹)

$$UA_{\text{Con}} = 57.4025779 + 0.00525691221 \cdot n_{\text{Comp,HP}} - 1.22681609 \cdot t_{\text{ref,in}} + 0.105254656 \cdot t_{\text{wat,in}} + 0.996690148 \cdot p_{\text{high}} + 3.30126524 \cdot \dot{m}_{\text{wat}}$$

$$UA_{\text{Des}} = 26.0046135 + 0.00156345858 \cdot n_{\text{Comp,HP}} - 0.0798242793 \cdot t_{\text{ref,in}} - 0.617720842 \cdot t_{\text{wat,in}} + 0.242269612 \cdot \dot{m}_{\text{wat}} + 0.775917432 \cdot p_{\text{high}}$$

$$UA_{\text{Sub}} = 40.3859428 + 0.00472577607 \cdot n_{\text{Comp,HP}} - 1.21052722 \cdot t_{\text{ref,in}} + 0.168414876 \cdot t_{\text{wat,in}} - 2.587743253.6 \cdot \dot{m}_{\text{wat}} + 1.01065452 \cdot p_{\text{high}}$$

$$UA_{\text{Eva}} = 103.682221 - 0.478449207 \cdot \dot{m}_{\text{ref}} + 0.0744936997 \cdot n_{\text{Comp,CH}}$$

APPENDIX B – Boundary conditions for measurement and simulation

OP-Nr.	$n_{\text{COMP,HP}}$ [$\frac{1}{\text{min}}$]	$t_{\text{CH,SO,in}}$ [°C]	$t_{\text{CH,SO,out}}$ [°C]	$t_{\text{HP,SI,in}}$ [°C]	p_{mean} [bar]	$\Delta T_{\text{sub,HP}}$ [K]	$\dot{V}_{\text{CH,SO}}$ [$\frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{h}}$]	$\dot{V}_{\text{HP,SI}}$ [$\frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{h}}$]
1	1800	4.3	1	62	13.5	11.95	159.5	23.04
2	904	4	1.09	61	13.5	6.56	174.3	23.976
3	904	4.11	1.11	68	13.5	6.25	174.3	23.868
4	904	4.04	0.88	60	13.5	14.3	172.5	7.416
5	1800	3.69	1.03	65	15.5	12.49	175.9	23.508
6	1800	3.6	0.95	65	15.5	12.44	175.9	23.508
7	1800	2.79	1.02	60	13.5	12.02	175.1	23.04
8	1800	2.93	1.06	59	13.5	13.22	175.1	15.264
9	1800	3	1.03	58	13.5	13.74	174.5	15.084
10	1800	2.92	0.99	62	13.5	12.81	167.2	12.924
11	1800	3.91	1.05	62	13.5	12.97	173.8	13.14
12	1800	3.81	0.87	67	13.5	12.77	161.4	13.284
13	1800	3.79	1.07	64	13.5	2.8	171.4	15.084
14	1187	3.6	1.05	69	13.5	8.21	161.6	22.86
15	1800	3.63	1.09	69	13.5	11.12	171.9	22.86
16	1800	3.97	1.07	71	13.5	10.89	172.1	22.788
17	1800	3.81	1.04	66	13.5	14.95	176.4	18.468
18	1800	3.4	1.05	68	13.5	14.63	176.5	18.576
19	1800	3.63	1.01	69	13.5	11.58	168.2	23.292
20	1800	3.53	1	67	13.5	11.71	174.5	23.328
21	1800	3.89	1.01	65	13.5	11.26	170	23.292
22	1800	3.88	1.16	61	13.5	11.52	178.8	24.084
23	1800	2.98	1.08	60	13.5	11.95	173.8	23.148
24	1800	3.1	0.99	72	13.5	11.12	175.3	22.824
25	1800	2.98	0.93	68	13.5	11.12	174.3	22.86
26	1028	3.08	1.06	71	13.5	6.65	193	22.68
27	1078	3.1	0.96	71	13.5	7.12	190	22.68
28	1043	4.13	1.14	71	13.5	6.91	190.2	22.608
29	1016	3.65	0.93	71	13.5	6.51	184.2	22.824
30	997	4.15	0.91	72	13.5	6.29	165.6	22.716